

CNN based Interpretability Analysis of Voiceprint Recognition

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Abstract: Voiceprint recognition is a type of biometric recognition which converts acoustic signals into electrical signals and then uses computers for recognition. Voiceprint recognition is widely used, for example, power companies use it to detect equipment failures, while environmental protection administration institutions use it to monitor ecological status. In particular, when used in bird sound recognition, we can monitor ecological diversity of jungles, swamps, to prevent birds from colliding with aircraft, and to provide a rigor reference for the differential prevention and control of electric transmission line bird failures. The community have devoted to various models that use deep learning to improve voiceprint recognition. However, the popular neural network models suffer from insufficient interpretability, so do neural network-based voiceprint recognition models. In order to interpret the model behavior more intuitively, such as how deep learning makes such a prediction, why some features are favored over others by a model, we look for the determinants of the spectrogram for the final voiceprint recognition in an image recognition network through an interpretable analysis of the neural network. We use a CNN-based image recognition network and apply it to the more challenging Kaggle Rainforest Bird dataset. In this interpretable framework, it is modified such that filters are encouraged to learn more interpretable parameters so that features can be easily identified in a spectrogram. Spectrograms where bird sound occurs are called key spectrograms, while spectrograms where no bird sound occurs are called non-key spectrograms. Experimental results visualize the differences of key spectrograms from non-key spectrograms in the time and frequency dimensions. Meanwhile, we compare the key spectrograms of higher recognition rate with those of lower recognition rate and find the former have more salient features

Keywords: Voiceprint Recognition, Spectrogram, Image Classification, CNN, Interpretability

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Introduction

Over the last few years, deep neural networks (DNNs) have achieved tremendous success [8] in computer vision [5], [7], speech recognition [11], natural language processing [14] and other fields [20]. However, deep learning works as a black box model and it is difficult to explain its underlying mechanism and behaviors. For example, Szegedy et al. [15] found a way that could arbitrarily change the network's prediction by applying a certain imperceptible change to the input image. Nguyen et al. [10] showed another way to produce completely unrecognizable images, which are recognized as certain objects by DNNs with 99.99% confidence. Their observations suggest that even though DNNs can achieve superior performance on many tasks, their underlying mechanisms may be very different from those of humans'

and have not yet been well-understood. Questions are often asked such as how deep learning makes such a prediction, why some features are favored over others by a model, and what changes are needed to improve model performance, etc. [3]. Unfortunately, only modest success has been made to answer these questions. Interpretability [19] refers to having a reasonable explanation for the trained model in deep learning. The academic community is trying to understand the decision-making process and results of deep learning models, and explain the internal workings of the models.

Residual neural networks with split-attention mechanisms can get higher voice recognition accuracy than convolutional neural networks. However, this type of model is still constrained by the opacity of the classification results and the inherent bias of neural networks. In Kaggle Data Science Competition “Rainforest Connection Species Audio Detectio”, we extend AdaS-ResNeSt from ResNeSt, a residual neural network. AdaS (Adaptive Scheduling of Stochastic Gradients) optimizer and data augmentation are introduced. Experiments on Kaggle Rainforest Bird show that the accuracy of model reaches 0.982 and Macro F1 is 0.782. Experiments on ST-AEDS-201801001 show that AdaS-ResNeSt works almost perfect in speaker Recognition with F1 value 0.996 [4]. The same model exhibits different performance with F1 on different dataset, we attempt to interpret Kaggle Rainforest Bird with lower F1. In this work, a convolutional neural network with filters is used to identify interpretable features and activation regions for image classification. The difference between this network and traditional convolutional neural networks lies in the calculation of the filter layer loss. By setting excitement filters to learn more interpretable parameters, targets and features in the image become more recognizable, and the final interpretable results are presented on the spectrogram.

2. Related Works

Since the breakthrough of Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) in the ImageNet competition in 2012, deep learning-based image recognition has become popular. This approach benefits from feature learning, as shown in Fig. 1, where small features in the zebra image are extracted by convolutional layers and then reduced in dimension by pooling layers. Additionally, CNN-based methods have also been adopted in music retrieval [12], extensively used in noise segmentation [6] and chord recognition [9].

Fig. 1: Architecture of a Convolution Neural Network

Many researchers have done related work on interpretability in DNNs. In 2018, Chunyang Wu et al. [17] proposed a scheme called activation regularization, which is applied to the output of activation functions to improve the interpretability and regularization of networks and encourages outputs of activation function to match target patterns. By defining appropriate target patterns, different learning concepts can be applied to the network. In the same year, Mirco Ravanelliet al. [13] developed a neural architecture that can effectively process audio waveforms and proposed

SincNet, a novel convolutional neural network (CNN) that encourages the first layer to discover meaningful filters by using parameterized sinc functions. Compared to standard CNNs, it learns all elements of each filter, and only the low and high cutoff frequencies of bandpass filters are learned directly from the data.

Fig. 2 Interpretability Experiments for Junco Bird, Corn, and Wheaten Terrier from [1]

Results from different interpretability experiments for junco bird, corn, and wheaten terrier [1] are shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that deep learning models have high accuracy in handling complex data tasks such as image and audio recognition classification. However, the reliability of their judgments still cannot be completely trusted, so most deep learning models have not yet been applied in fields such as transportation, medical diagnosis, financial risk assessment, and legal decision-making. Interpretability can not only improve the reliability of models, but also improve the legitimacy of model and confidences of users, thereby promote the widespread application of deep learning models and improve the value and effectiveness of models.

3. Design and Methodology

3.1 Target of Interpretability

$$T_{\text{Interpretability}} = \text{Argmax}_E Q(E | \text{Model}, \text{Human}, \text{Data}, \text{Task}) \tag{1}$$

The target of interpretability is shown in Formular 1, where Q is an interpretable evaluation equation, and E is a specific method for implementing interpretability. The entire process is to find an explanation method that uses given specific data ($Data$) and a specific task ($Task$) for a particular model ($Model$) that maximizes understanding for a specific population with relevant expertise ($Human$).

3.2 Creating Category Activation Maps on Spectrograms

In visual image recognition tasks, the image contour plays a vital role. However, in audio recognition tasks, spectrograms and sonograms [18] are mainly composed of continuous and smooth gradients and there are not only local correlations but also global correlations such as harmonic structures [2] and rhythmic events. We visualize the features of spectrograms by modifying the convolutional structure. By convolutional layers, it is possible to understand on which part of the input image the filter is focusing.

Fig3. Distinction between General CNN and Explainable CNN

Fig. 3 shows the structure difference between a regular CNN and an interpretable CNN. In a regular CNN, a convolutional layer can be described as a representation where filters may be activated by a cat's head and legs and the complex representation in this convolutional layer decrease the interpretability of the network. In contrast, in an interpretable convolutional neural network, the convolutional layer is directly activated by a specific part, allowing us to identify which target parts will be remembered and classified by the convolutional layer. We hope the convolutional kernel can match the features of related categories in the spectrogram.

The mechanism of interpretable CNN is as follows: modify the loss of filters in the higher convolutional layer to reduce the entropy of activation between different categories and the entropy of spatial distribution of neuron activation. From the perspective of whole CNN model, by replacing the higher convolutional layer and adding an interpretable layer [16], we can fine-tune and train an interpretable model. This model can activate the unique parts contained in the same target category. For example, the left and right eyes of the same cat, although both are eyes, will be represented by different filters because the two eyes are symmetrical but not the identical.

The configuration of the interpretable convolutional layer is crucial. A filter in a convolutional layer corresponds to a category, and images from different categories cannot activate the filters in the convolutional layer. The formula to determine the category is as follows:

$$\hat{c} = \operatorname{argmax}_c \operatorname{mean}_{x=f(I):I \in I_c} \sum_{ij} x_{ij} \tag{2}$$

In formula 2, x_{ij} corresponds to the feature map, and I_c corresponds to the image category. The category corresponding to resulting maximum value by summing the feature maps by category is that of the image that can automatically activate the filter.

Fig. 4 T_{μ_i} Template

$$T^- = (t_{ij}^-), t_{ij}^- = -\tau < 0 \tag{3}$$

The negative template of filter that cannot activate the convolution core is shown in formula 3. If it does not match the category of the filter, it fails to pass the activation function of ReLU. The T_{μ_i} template is shown in Fig. 4. When the target part mainly triggers the i -th unit in x , each part matches the feature map x . As can be seen from the figure, the closer it is to the category of the filter, the more the color tends to dark yellow, and vice versa, the color tends to dark blue.

For a template with $n \times n$ grid, position where activation is successful is:

$$T_{\mu} = (t_{ij}^+), t_{ij}^+ = \tau \cdot \max\left(1 - \beta \frac{|i-j| - \mu_1}{n}, -1\right) \tag{4}$$

The total number of templates is n^2 plus one negative template.

$$T = \{T^-, T_{\mu_1}, T_{\mu_2}, \dots, T_{\mu_{n^2}}\} \tag{5}$$

An interpretable convolutional neural network (CNN) is trained using an end-to-end approach. During the forward propagation process, each filter passes information from bottom to top, as in traditional CNNs. During the backpropagation process, each interpretable filter is influenced by both the gradient loss and the filter's own loss,

$$\frac{\partial \text{Loss}}{\partial x_{ij}} = \lambda \frac{\partial \text{Loss}_f}{\partial x_{ij}} + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=k}^N \frac{\partial L(\hat{y}_k, y_k^*)}{\partial x_{ij}} \tag{6}$$

where x_{ij} represents the feature map, $L(\hat{y}_k, y_k^*)$ represents the final task loss of x_{ij} from the k th sample, Loss_f represents the loss of the filter, λ represents the weight, $\frac{\partial \text{Loss}}{\partial x_{ij}}$ is backpropagated to the next layer, and the gradient is calculated and the parameters of the CNN are updated in the next layer.

Fig. 5 Training Loss of Traditional CNN

Therefore, by training interpretable CNN in this way, it can recognize the features in the image, classify them into the desired categories, and represent the features of the image category by category activation maps.

4. Evaluation and Results

Training and validation were conducted on basic CNN model and improved explainable CNN model to evaluate the impact of different models on the accuracy of spectrograms recognition. The Kaggle Rainforest Bird dataset was used and we classify audios by recognizing their corresponding spectrograms.

At first, the spectrogram converted from the audio was classified by traditional CNN. The change of loss value during the training process with the epoch is shown in Fig. 5. It can be seen from the figure that the change of loss value in the first epoch implies that the machine has started to learn the rules. Between the first and eighth epoch, the loss value continues to decrease slowly and finally approaches 0, indicating that the training results of the machine is continuously improved. The final recognition accuracy of the experiment is about 0.7.

Fig. 6 Validation and Test Loss of Traditional CNN

These two figures show the changes of the loss with epochs during the validation and test phases of traditional CNN. It can be seen that the loss value fluctuates dramatically during the validation and test process, indicating that the model cannot fit the data very well. For traditional CNNs applied in spectrograms, the model parameters need to be adjusted and the training process needs to be optimized to improve the model's performance. The final validation accuracy was 0.67, and the test accuracy reached 0.68, which is consistent with the expected results.

As shown in Fig. 7, the training process started with a significant decrease in the loss value from 3.5 to 1.25 within the first epoch, indicating significant progress in the machine's understanding the relationship between input data and expected output. The loss value continued to decrease in the subsequent learning process, and at the end of the eighth epoch, it was almost close to 0, indicating that the training had reached a stable convergent state. The final recognition rate is about 0.7.

Fig. 7 Training Loss of Explainable CNN

As the epochs of verifications increases, the model's loss value cannot tend to a stable convergence state, instead it shows rising fluctuations. The final validation accuracy was 0.68 and the test accuracy reached 0.69.

Fig. 8 Validation and Test Loss of Explainable CNN

Fig. 9 Category Activation Maps for Categories with Higher Accuracy

Fig. 9 presents category activation maps of spectrograms where time is on the horizontal axis, and frequency is on the vertical axis. The distribution time of Rainforest Birds' sound in each audio file is irregular. From Fig. 9, it can be observed that in the categories with high accuracy of training results (such as s3, s16 and s10), the location of the birds' sound corresponds to that of the difference point where the original color appears. This indicates that bird sound belonging to the corresponding category appears. For categories with high recognition accuracy, they will be activated after passing the convolutional layer filter, so the position of the spectrogram's activation map will be more salient.

Fig. 10 Category Activation Maps for Categories with Lower Accuracy

Contrary to Fig. 9, Fig. 10 presents the categories with lower accuracy in Kaggle Rainforest Bird (such as s7, s13, and s21). It can be seen from the category activation maps that spectrograms are difficult to produce color differences in the frequency dimension. In interpretable CNN, these types of Rainforest Bird cannot be detected and activated by the filters in the convolutional layer, and the filters cannot be stimulated to learn more meaningful features. The most really important challenges of this experiment are: the application of the modified loss function to the Kaggle Rainforest Bird dataset, the qualitative and quantitative analysis of the activated regions in the spectrogram. That is, the actual verification of interpretability is a complex and cumbersome process. More generally, tradeoff between interpretability and performance is a difficult problem.

5. Conclusion

We aim to analyze the impact of interpretability on deep learning models, starting from the perspective of interpretable CNNs, adjusting the filters of the convolutional layers in order to experiment on the Kaggle Rainforest Bird dataset, highlighting the features of categories in the spectrogram. The results show that interpretability highlights the features of categories in spectrograms, and provides a working direction for improving the reliability and accuracy of deep learning models.

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